

A 3-dimensional fast machine learning algorithm for mobile unmanned aerial vehicle base stations

Wasswa Shafik¹, S. Mojtaba Matinkhah², Solagbade Saheed Afolabi³, Mamman Nur Sanda⁴

^{1,2}Department of Computer Engineering, Yazd University, Iran

³Department of Mineral Chemistry, Yazd University, Iran

⁴Department of Condensed Matter Physics, Yazd University, Iran

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 10, 2020

Revised Sep 2, 2020

Accepted Sep 29, 2020

Keywords:

Beam selection

Multi-armed bandit

Reinforcement learning

Unmanned aerial vehicle

ABSTRACT

The 5G technology is predicted to achieve the unoptimized millimeter Wave (mmWave) of 30-300 GHz bands. This unoptimized band because of the loss of mm-Wave bands, like path attenuation and propagation losses. Nonetheless, because of: (i) directional transmission paving way for beamforming to recompense for the path attenuation, and (ii) sophisticated placement concreteness of the base stations (BS) is the best alternative for array wireless communications in mmWave bands (that is to say 100-150 m). The advance in technology and innovation of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) necessitates many opportunities and uncertainties. UAVs are agile and can fly all complexities if the terrains making ground robots unsuitable. The UAV may be managed either independently through aboard computers or distant controlled of a flight attendant on pulverized wireless communication links in our case 5G. Although a fast algorithm solved the problematic aspect of beam selection for 2-dimensional scenarios. This paper presents 3-dimensional scenarios for UAV. We modeled beam selection with environmental responsiveness in millimeter Wave UAV to accomplish close optimum assessments on the regular period through learning from the available situation.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

S. Mojtaba Matinkhah

Department of Computer Engineering

Yazd University

Yazd Province, Safaeiah-Pazhoohesh Street, Yazd, Iran

Email: matinkah@yazd.ac.ir

1. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning (ML) being a part of the artificial intelligence, it has influenced some communication like in broadcast communication well detailed in where ML can be used in extending parameters during connectivity remote areas either positively or negatively including information retrievals, internet of Things that entails UAVs, media and web communication, online making, monetization, mining, quality of services in web qualities, web security and privacy issues in social networks among others [1-11]. Machine Learning (ML) being a part of the artificial intelligence, it has influenced numerous communication like in broadcast communication well detailed in where ML can be used in extending parameters during connectivity remote areas either positively or negatively including information retrievals, internet of Things that entails UAVs, media and web communication, online making, monetization, mining, quality of services in web qualities, web security and privacy issues in social networks as we early depicted in the social web of Things and other computing paradigms [12, 13]. Diverse engineering corporations have on track to detriment from unmanned aerial vehicles, such as agroindustry for exactness agronomy procedures, movie productions,

and rescue branches for artificial disaster assignments. Nevertheless, the mentioned contemporary unmanned aerial vehicles profitably applications necessities an unmanned aerial vehicles operative that aviators the automobile exploit tenuously control policies. As an alternative, cargo logistics and scattering manufacturing arenas are concerned in the request of self-directed unmanned aerial vehicles for the manipulation of processes other ways might origin far-reaching variations in equal departments of cargo logistics and distribution tasks and cities. Consequently, it is significant to address the devotion to confident unmanned aerial vehicles' technological traits whose considerate can aid in an evaluation of the tangible prospect of such UAVs in executing distributions and connectivity in the city context demonstrated in Figure 1 environment. Issues of drones can be classified in different ways like morally, ethically, and legally through which numerous studies have been done like Chattopadhyay [14] proposes non-orthogonal multiple access schemes aimed at the 5G UAV communications. The author depicted that the systems with a non-orthogonal multiple accesses overtake other compound admittance schemes in standings of quantity volume, dynamism effectiveness, and Spectral effectiveness. Notably, the proposed multiple access schemes accomplish enhanced sum-rate at a subordinate elevation which diminishes the complete dynamism outflow of the unmanned aerial vehicles.

El-Sayed et al. [15] deployed UAVs to act as moveable edges following circulation procedures and overcrowding environments. In their study, the proposed a traffic-aware approach for permitting the placement of unmanned aerial vehicles in vehicular situations. The recreational grades depicted the projected technique can accomplish occupied system attention under diverse circumstances deprived of the extra announcement above or interruption. Xu et al. [16] collectively proposed a model to handle the gains of the fifth generation mm-Wave detector and ML techniques to recognize the "black flying" UAV. The study more still delivers an operative elucidation to resolve the tricky of discovering and recognizing UAV through a 5G mm-wave detector in the IoT that is highly concrete submission. This is a first project in the UAV research field presenting a set of possible better beam selection scenarios in 3D. It has not emerged due to the technological inadequacy of 4G and its associated limitation. Superficially, UAVs were put into exists to support military missions. However, it has crossed to other areas like agriculture, business goods transportation search, and rescue operation among others. The UAV in this research is used as a base station since the current situation is fixed with a major problem of inaccessibility of signal to receivers. In appreciation to the current UAV studies, conducted studies show that there is still a need to explicitly investigate UAVs' communication, security, privacy, device to device (UAV to other devices) factors. This project mainly focused on the UAV communication efficiency in 3D where UAV is considered to be a base station as compared to other alternative approaches to service delivery. Pěnička et al. [17] proposed a variable neighborhood search with the applicable optimum sampling-based probable procedures attitude for records gathering forecasting for UAVs in a city atmosphere with complications like blockages among others. Vladuta et al. [18] used UAVs for data gathering from wireless sensors. They proposed a self-motivated erection of the path (route) that UAVs use in information collection using wireless sensors on their locations.

The main contributions of the paper are summarized. (i) Modeling of the beam selection of millimeter Wave base stations by way of a MAB approach. The archetypal model is geometric, where the model is modestly adjustable to diverse situations. (ii) Availing and provision of the original circumstantial online algorithm for beam selection in millimeter Wave BS. The system empowers the BSs to independently cram every respective beam's records, deprived of necessitating a training stage. (iii) Providing and contributing to the systematic superior bound on the regret that demonstrates the conjunction of Fast Machine Learning to the optimum selections. (iv) Establishment of using the wide-ranging model for instance with animate and emblematic traffic configurations gotten from Google Maps of the desired locations. Numerous models currently have been proposed in managing beams and selection. Deng et al. [19] considered relay selection and beam selection in two-hop D2D relaying 5G networks. The authors recycled unscrupulous dispatch assortment and millimeter Wave equivalent beamforming to frontier the gesticulating overhead. Giordani et al. [20] propose enhancements for the beam administration measures encompassed in the new radio access technology stipulations established on equally impartial and another manner. The authors also recommend scheme constraints interrelated to beam controlling contexts. Wang et al. [21] worked on satellite-constructed IoT. They proposed multiple beamforming for numerous managers in the viewpoint sphere. The quantity of respective beamforming been nominated for the conduit dimension is cushioned, and adapts the prospect of the arbitrary collection of grins.

The selection of the best beam from a discrete codebook in which digital precoding and analog beamforming are combined. They designed an iterative system to modernize the shaft of the beam for auxiliary enactment enhancement. Pal et al. [22] propose a heuristic greedy algorithm for beam selection in which users functioning at mm-Wave incidences and fortified with a hefty quantity of tentacle rudiments at the admittance fact. They also propose another approach established on the Kuhn-Munkres procedure and

familiarize an innovative official context for the beam. Furthermore, an access point with a given number of portion tentacle assortments interconnects with a given number of users respectively obligating a distinct protuberance. Their delinquent is choosing a given beam with the entirety rate as the enactment metric. The modeled ray miscellany as a bilateral identical amongst the two sets of players and contemplate dualistic diverse techniques of demonstrating the player's predilections. Meng et al. [23] proposed BeamRaster, a precoding scheme, for massive multiple users' multiple inputs and multiple harvest classifications. The structure pre-subtracts a customary of perspective-domain beam strainers which rifts the frequency hooked on maneuvering subspaces. Through a discordant bench of the trajectory the relationship amongst a stream of beams in instantaneous, and via an interference-awareness of user-beam assortment, and lastly through a pre-distortion technique to scratch the outstanding meddling due to the side-lobes, BeamRaster manages the cross-interference. The software-defined radio platform and replications through extensive projections spectacle that approach can accomplish a higher capability achievement. Antón-Haro and Mestre [24] investigate how angle-of-arrival facts might be subjugated via extreme learning, deep learning, or any other ML tactics to complete beam assortment in the uplink of a millimeter Wave communication scheme. Twofold administered ML methodologies approached are: firstly, the k -adjacent neighbors and sustenance trajectory classifiers; and secondly, the feed-forward unfathomable neural systems: the multiple-layer perceptron's. They compared the sum-rate of their proposal with exhaustive search.

Jiang and Jafarkhani [25] proposed a beamforming scheme that optimizes the improvement and inter-user intrusion at an identical stretch. Above and beyond, the authors premeditated a vigorous beamforming structure to deliver sturdiness in contradiction of defective frequency data. More still, they demonstrated that the anticipated non-robust multi-user equivalent beamformer outdoes the outdated equivalent beamforming technique after the SNR-effect is in height and the planned vigorous beamformer may deliver over 110% enhancement in the sum-rate associated through the beam techniques of selection.

Above all these models proposed, none of them address remote access communication like in valleys below the line of sites, help in time of danger and also optimized beam selection in approach to average data to be received, the impact of fixed base stations, the impact of selected beams, impact on blockages, live daily traffic patterns among others. These justify the need to have deep study cover all the above features mentioned that the current features are not approaching at all possible applications require little or no human intervention and thus must have the ability to operate autonomously through the use of global maps like Google Maps. These justify the need to have an in-depth study cover all the above features mentioned that the current features are not approaching at all possible applications require little or no human intervention and thus must have the ability to operate autonomously through the use of a global map like presented in Figure 1.

Figure. 1. The simulation atmosphere. The trolleys with bus momentarily block red car with black car correspondingly

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Model description

The mUBS assumed a predetermined set ξ Φ is denoted as $|\hat{n}|$ discrete not non-right angles (non-orthogonal) UAV beams. The model adopted that the mUBS might solitary select a subsection of bm beams concurrently noting that $bm \in \xi, bm \prec \xi$, remains considered to be an immobile amount. Some of the limitations identified on mmWave channel sparsity. The main reason for the mUBS stands to select a subsection of bm that will be maximizing the number of records magnificently expected by the approaching CR in the reportage zone. The model further adopted the fact that the mUBS is not certain or no nothing about then environment. Normally, in this situation, the complication of the complex application reduces as the operative necessities nothing to be configured like at each mUBS according to the environment. Therefore, the mUBS has to learn as the situation changes to select the subset of the beams. In this way, the UAV will be to account for every approaching CR in context to beams it emits. We will also take in mind a distinct-interval situation, given that the mUBS informs that the beam in the steady interval setup in every a setup or period $x=1, \dots, N$, given that $N \in \mathbb{N}$ also considered to be a finite horizon; the following three activities are applied.

- a. A section $\theta_t = \{CR_{u,i}\} i = 1, \dots, \dots \theta_t$ is given that $CR_t = |\theta_t|$ CR like automobiles, different IoTs mong others to the mUBS. The number CR_t of the CRs fulfills the condition that $CR_t \leq \theta_{max}$ considering the $\theta_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$ will be the extreme sum reinforced CRs within the coverage area. At the time of the registration, mUBS will be having the capacity to receive data about the situation it, z of every forthcoming automobile $CR_{u,z}$, will be a realistic trajectory reserved from the constrained coverage area $P = [0,1,2]^p$.
- b. The mUBS chooses a subsection of bm . The study also denotes that the customers of particular beams in the retro in the interval z by $St = \{st, l\} l = 1, \dots, bm \subseteq \xi$. Formerly the CR in the Θ_t will be informed about the nominated rays through CR boundary.
- c. At the time, in case the CR_u will be within the range of mUBS coverage area according to google map and mUBS will be in a position to transmit data to any CR within the coverage area. Observation will be considered on the amount of data $A_{od,l}(pt, l, t)$ CR Cru will be productively be received by selected beams $A_{od,l}, l = 1, \dots, bm$, till the end of the z .

Denoting that the random variable $rb(x)$ the beam enactment of bm under the context of the x . It will be meaning that the quantity of records $rb(x)$ of CR with the context $P \in \xi$ will be receiving after the mUBS using the $bm \in \xi$. The study presumed that this arbitrary adaptable is constrained in $[0,1, M_{Aod}]$, given M_{Aod} will be the all-out sum of records which may be acknowledged by CR. M_{Aod} will be restricted by the all-out degree of the broadcast channel. We denoted the expected value of the beam performance of the beam bm in the situation p with $\mu_b(x)$.

The mUBS ambitions at choosing a subgroup of the beams that maximizes the predictable receive records at CR. Therefore, the optimal subset in period t $V_t^*(P_t) = \{V_{t,l}^*(P_t)\} l = 1, \dots, \dots, bm \subseteq \xi$. Therefore the customer $V_t^*(P_t)$ will be depending on $X_t = \{xt, i\} i = 1, \dots, \dots, \Theta_t$ and bm satisfy (1)

$$V_t^*(P_t) \in \underset{bm \in \xi \setminus \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^{l-1} \{V_{t,k}^*(P_t)\} \right)}{\arg \max} \sum_{z=1}^g \mu_{bm}(pt, z) \tag{1}$$

Noting that $j=1, bm$. In case the mUBS will know the expected beam performance $\mu_b(x)$. For every CR situation $p \in X$ and each beam $bm \in \xi$, it will be selected optimum subsection of the beam for every regular of forthcoming CR. To obtain the expected amount, the data will be received over the sequence from 1 to the time T that obtained (2).

$$\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} E \left[r_{t,l}^*(pt) (xt, t) \right] = \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} \mu_{t,l}^*(xt) (xt, z) \quad (2)$$

The mUBS does not recognize the coverage area; it will be learning the expected performance $\mu_b(x)$. Over a given period (3), to acquire the identified concerns, the mUBS requires attempting diverse beams of diverse CR situation completed stretch similarly ensuring that the beams will be proved in being good. Lastly, the learning algorithm will be done some times for CR in the coverage area in the context of P_t , selecting the St of bm .

Pseudocode of proposed reinforcement algorithm

1. Input: $T, PT, K(t)$
2. Initialize context partition: Create partition P_T of context space $[0,1,2]^X$ into $(P_T)^X$ hypercubes of identical sizes
3. Initialize counters: For all $b \in B$ and all $h \in P_T$ set $N_{b,h} = 0$
4. Initialize estimates: For all $b \in B$ and all $h \in P_T$, set $\mu'_{b,h} = 0$
5. for each $t = 1, \dots, T$ do
6. Observe vehicle contexts $X_t = \{x_t, i\} i = 1, \dots, V_t$
7. Find $H_t = \{h_t, i\} i = 1, \dots, V_t$ such that $x_{t,i} \in p_{t,i} \in p_T, i = 1, \dots, V_t$
8. Compute the set of under-explored beams $B_{H_t}^{ue}(t)$ in (5)
9. if $B_{H_t}^{ue}(t) \neq 0$ then Exploration
10. $u = size(B_{H_t}^{ue}(t))$
11. if $u \geq m$ then
12. select $s_t, 1, \dots, s_{t,m}$ randomly from $B_{H_t}^{ue}(t)$
13. else
14. select $s_t, 1, \dots, s_{t,u}$ as u beams from $B_{H_t}^{ue}(t)$
15. select $s_{t,u+1}, \dots, s_{t,m}$ as the $(m-u)$ beams from (6)
- $b'_1, H_t(t), \dots, b'_{m-u}, H_t(t)$
16. else if
17. else
18. select $s_t, 1, \dots, s_{t,m}$ as the m beams
- $b'_1, H_t(t), \dots, b'_{m-u}, H_t(t)$ from (7)
19. end if
20. Observe the received data $r_{j,i}$ of each vehicle $V_{t,i} i = 1, \dots, V_t$ in each beam $s_{t,j}, j = 1, \dots, m$
21. for $i = 1, \dots, V_t$ do
22. for $j = 1, \dots, m$ do
- $\mu'_{s_{t,j}, i} = \frac{\mu'_{s_{t,j}, i} + r_{j,i}}{N_{s_{t,j}, h_{t,i}} + 1}$ and $N_{s_{t,j}, h_{t,i}} = N_{s_{t,j}, h_{t,i}} + 1$
- 23.
24. end for
25. end for
26. end for

The collection of the erudition will be depending on the history of the beams to be selected (4). The anticipated quantity of records conventional by the vehicle will be given as follows in case we consider the selection $St, t=1, \dots, T$ of an algorithm.

$$\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} E \left[r_{st,j} (pt, z) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} E \left[\mu_{st,l(pt)}(pt, i) - r_{st,l}(pt, i) \right] \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the anticipated modification in the quantity of conventional information completed and an algorithm will be the "learning regret" taken to be R considering both (2) and (4). Following the formulation of the last equation conclusively leading to the $R(T)$ produced by the (5) and (6) respectively.

$$R(T) = E \left[\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} \left(r_{t,l(pt)}^*(pt, z) - r_{st,l(pt)}(pt, z) \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

$$R(T) = \left[\sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{z=1}^{q_t} \sum_{l=1}^{bm} \left(\mu_{t,l(pt)}^*(pt, z) - E \left[r_{st,l(pt)}(pt, z) \right] \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

2.2. Learning technique

The proposed model of selecting beam in an mUBS as a fast 3-dimension semi-online learning problem as depicted in the algorithm below since it allows the identification of the best beams independently in a prearranged interval while secretarial for self-motivated traffic and atmosphere changes depicted in the Algorithm I pseudo code below. Henceforth, the mUBS necessities to categorize the superlative beam through prudently choosing subcategories of beams over a certain interval. This tactic cascades beneath the classification of appropriate MAB difficulties. Such issues furthermore contain side data that touches the rewards of the movements. A contextual multi-armed bandit approach will appreciate the mUBS does not modestly absorb, or inferior which beams are untouchable on unvarying, then again in its place it exploits superfluous evidence about imminent CR to distinguish which beams are the superlative underneath an assumed traffic condition as the procedure clarifies.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND SIMULATION

Briefly, this section presents a discussion of the provided simulation results in Figure 2, and a detailed explanation of the algorithm presented obtained from the simulation of the channel description presented in Table 1 and from parameters inputs in Table 2.

Figure 2. Impact of blockages on the cumulative received data for an arrival rate of specified λ and time

Table 1. Channel parameters

Parameters	Values and Notations
Carrier regularity	28 Gigahertz
Bandwidth	1 Gigahertz
Transmit Power	30 decibels
Path loss Model (dB)	$32.4 + 17.3 \log_{10} d(m) + 20 \log_{10} (f_c(GHz)) + \xi$
Noise figure	4 decibels Automobile
UAV's beam width	36°
Simulator tool	NS3
Thermo Noise	-174 dBm/Hz

Table 2. Simulation inputs and specifications

Input parameters:	Specification	Channel load	Mean Absolute Deviation results
β	0.100000 veh/m	$\rho = 0.23, \alpha = 0.058415$	Optimal 1.60
λ	10 Hz	$\rho = 0.23, \alpha = 0.058415$	2D FML 0.19
Pt	20 dBm	$\rho = 0.23, \alpha = 0.058415$	2D FML 0.21
S	2 subchannels	$\rho = 0.23, \alpha = 0.058415$	UCB 0.07
B	190 bytes	$\rho = 0.23, \alpha = 0.058415$	Random 1.25
β	0.200000 veh/m	$\rho = 0.44, \alpha = 0.478921$	Optimal 0.91
λ	10 Hz	$\rho = 0.44, \alpha = 0.478921$	2D FML 0.16
Pt	20 dBm	$\rho = 0.44, \alpha = 0.478921$	2D FML 0.18
S	4 subchannels	$\rho = 0.44, \alpha = 0.478921$	UCB 0.07
B	190 bytes	$\rho = 0.44, \alpha = 0.478921$	Random 0.83
β	0.300000 veh/m	$\rho = 0.62, \alpha = 0.832470$	Optimal 0.92
λ	10 Hz	$\rho = 0.62, \alpha = 0.832470$	2D FML 0.14
Pt	20 dBm	$\rho = 0.62, \alpha = 0.832470$	3D FML 0.20
S	4 subchannels	$\rho = 0.62, \alpha = 0.832470$	UCB 0.07
B	190 bytes	$\rho = 0.62, \alpha = 0.832470$	Random 0.84

3.1. Acclimatizing on structural dynamics

The result of the assessment is rummage-sale to acclimatize to structural diminuendos like the attendance of obstructions and deviations in traffic configurations. The procedure distinguishes blockages by assessing the cumulative traditional records of the respective automobile for the correspondingly nominated beam. Furthermore, the algorithm acclimates to road traffic patterns by the erudition of the association amongst the route of onset and the acknowledged records. As a result, it chooses the bms, which exploit the complete system aptitude. Consequently, it delivers the supplementary remainder to the thoroughfares with sophisticated traffic and hereafter, serves an outstanding quantity of automobiles. The model the delinquent as that MAB problem where frequent disputes in wireless infrastructures have been treated by the use of multi-armed bandits, a decision-maker has to choose a subdivision of activities of mysterious recompenses to achievement the recompense over the interval. In this perspective, a MAB method is significant for our delinquent subsequently an umBS uses an inadequate accustomed of beams instantaneously.

3.2. Communication on numerous facades

The Algorithms matches the issues of mmWave UAV communication on numerous facades are critically identified for instance Figure 2 identifies everlasting obstructions (structures), recurrently obstructed regions owing to temporary lockage's (case in example automobile stations) expending learning; Figure 3 depicts that controls traffic configurations to have scheme aptitude maximization by provided that grander treatment (like in this case apportionment of supplementary beams) in zones with weightier circulation important enhanced communication fatalities [26]. Within this learning section, the study adopted the algorithm that first took an attempt to develop and simulate fast learning where the environment of UAVs are studied and recognized by the UAV in the line of arrival to the base station, while supposing these arrivals are obtainable of the occasion of this daily, the study anticipated actions to categorize and acquire from such configurations [27].

Figure 3. Impact on the received bm data for arrival rate on cumulative received specified data

3.3. The general traffic patterns

This is significant since mm-Wave BS might communicate instantaneously above a restricted quantity of beams. This limit is subject to the hardware traits, the mmWave network, and the beamforming drill lastly Figure 4, on the list it conjectures traffic designs from the situation (like the automobile’s route of onset) and chooses the superlative beams. Figure 2, Time steps against the dissimilar cumulative regrets Note where the Orange color depicts Traditional methods, brown shows a single-dimensional, green color the 2-Dimensional and brown with the 3-dimensional algorithmic simulation.

Figure 4. Impact on the arrival rate λ of data based on the cumulative received data

3.4. A mount of assisted automobiles, and typical learning interval

The enactment metrics recycled in the estimations are collective and accumulative conventional records, the number of assisted-to automobiles, and normal learning intervals. The collective acknowledged data is discrete as the records received over completely the automobiles in the scheme in retro t. A collective acknowledged data is discrete as the data acknowledged complete overall the UAVs in the method in retro t. The acknowledged data are delineated equally as the data accepted completely via the UAVs in the scheme up to a specified period depicted in [28].

3.5. Animate regular traffic arrives

Using the focal approach to focus on conscious day-to-day traffic arrangement: The previous assessment stayed constructed on the characteristic traffic design demonstrated. Because of the optimizing magnitude, representative traffic-flows do not annexation the instantaneous variations in traffic arrangements that are distinguishable in sentient circulation description illustrated in Figure 5. Consequently, the study further noted that the investigational conscious traffic flow intelligence of Google for two days using half an hour interval. The study further nourished the gotten statistics to the simulant to estimate the enactment of algorithms in a conscious stream of traffic situations as per [29].

Figure 5. Aggregate received data for arrival rate with λ and β

3.6. The impact of blockages

The Impact of blockages was further investigated per the cumulative received data. To compute it in percentage, any percentage of permanent blockages, the proposed model outperformed all other currencies that are not optimum procedures. Increasing acknowledged data accomplished by our algorithms lies amongst 14.59% and 19.49% complex than that accomplished by the subsequent-superlative algorithm Upper Confidence Bound model portrayed below the outmoded reproductions. Furthermore, the model finalized the results diverge from that of Optimal merely by at most 3.91%. Lastly on the list are the variations in the graph domino influence from the quantity of UAVs in the scheme, the collective acknowledged data escalations with the number of UAVs depicting the average data received thus proper admission [30]. The Impact of blockages was further investigated per the cumulative received data. To compute it in percentage, any percentage of permanent blockages, the proposed model outperformed all other current non-optimal procedures Figure 6. The increasing received data accomplished by our algorithms lies amongst 14:59% and 19:49% to UCB model depicted under the traditional models in Figure 7. Furthermore, the model finalized the results diverge from that of Optimal merely by at most 3:91%.

Figure 6. Data for 172800 minutes of the live daily traffic pattern.

Figure 7. Impact on number of vehicles per time

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presented performance evaluation based on the emblematic traffic patterns, due to the averaging consequence, addressed a challenge of beam selection at millimeter Wave BS using multi-armed Bandits where the aftermath of the assortment is tremendously reliant on the traffic-flows and the obstructions like structures in the system. Objectively, the study proposed a Fast Machine Learning, a semi-algorithm per the multi-armed bandits that operate on negligible background network facts online learning as elucidated. This study did not focus on aviation paths standards against UAVs, UAV international policies too, assumptions, and restriction on UAVs in the geometric problem approach. Combining UAV localization and beam selection to maximize Efficiency has not been considered. This article has enthused us more to further lengthen this research to investigate the deep analysis of UAVs when used as a base station and its associated issues. In the future, the proposed model is to be subjected to other algorithms besides those that have been used in perspective to beam orthogonality, location recording, and situation of co-located automobiles, interference and number of selected beams.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the department members of Computer Engineering, Yazd University for sponsoring this work and editing for us to have this paper quality helped in UAV channel measurements and perfection.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. C. Saibabu, H. Sai, S. Yadav, and C. R. Srinivasan, "Synthesis of a model predictive controller for an identified model of MIMO process," *Int. J. Electr. Eng. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 950–956, 2020.
- [2] W. Shafik and S. A. Mostafavi, "Knowledge Engineering on Internet of Things through Reinforcement Learning," *Int J Comput Appl*, vol. 975, pp. 8887, 2020.
- [3] Z. Qin, Q. Yu, and M. J. Buehler, "Machine learning model for fast prediction of the natural frequencies of protein molecules," *RSC Adv.*, vol. 10, no. 28, pp. 16607–16615, 2020.
- [4] S. Mostafavi and W. Shafik, "Fog Computing Architectures, Privacy and Security Solutions," *J. Commun. Technol. Electron. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 24, pp. 1–14, 2019.
- [5] K. Wang, J. Luo, Y. Wei, K. Wu, J. Li, and Z. Chen, "Practical application of machine learning on fast phase equilibrium calculations in compositional reservoir simulations," *J. Comput. Phys.*, vol. 401, pp. 109013, 2020.
- [6] W. Shafik, M. Matinkhah, and M. N. Sanda, "Network Resource Management Drives Machine Learning: A Survey and Future Research Direction," *J. Commun. Technol. Electron. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 30, pp. 1–15, 2020.
- [7] W. Shafik, M. Matinkhah, M. Asadi, Z. Ahmadi, and Z. Hadiyan, "A Study on Internet of Things Performance Evaluation," *J. Commun. Technol. Electron. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 28, pp. 1–19, 2020.
- [8] W. Shafik, S. M. Matinkhah, and M. Ghasemzadeh, "Fog-Mobile Edge Performance Evaluation and Analysis on Internet of Things," *J. Adv. Res. Mob. Comput.*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2019.
- [9] W. Shafik, S. M. Matinkhah, and M. Ghasemzadeh, "Internet of Things-Based Energy Management, Challenges, and Solutions in Smart Cities," *J. Commun. Technol. Electron. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 27, pp. 1–11, 2020.
- [10] A. Patra and A. Suresh, "BLAZE: Blazing Fast Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning," *ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv200509042*, 2020.
- [11] W. Shafik, S. M. Matinkhah, and M. Ghasemzadeh, "A Fast Machine Learning for 5G Beam Selection for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Applications," *Inf. Syst. Telecommun.*, pp. 262, 2020.
- [12] W. Shafik and S. M. Matinkhah, "Privacy Issues in Social Web of Things," in *2019 5th International Conference on Web Research (ICWR)*, 2019, pp. 208–214.
- [13] L. Jiang and H. Jafarkhani, "Multi-User Analog Beamforming in Millimeter Wave MIMO Systems Based on Path Angle Information," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 608–619, Jan 2019.
- [14] S. CHATTOPADHYAY, "Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) for 5G networks and its application in unmanned aerial vehicle assisted communication," 16-Apr-2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/147329>. [Accessed: 06-Jul-2019].
- [15] H. El-Sayed, M. Chaqfa, S. Zeadally, and D. Putkal, "A Traffic-Aware Approach for Enabling Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in Smart City Scenarios," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 86297–86305, 2019.
- [16] F. Xu, T. Hong, J. Zhao, and T. Yang, "Detection and identification technology of rotor unmanned aerial vehicles in 5G scene," *Int. J. Distrib. Sens. Netw.*, vol. 15, no. 6, Jun. 2019.
- [17] R. Pěnička, J. Faigl, and M. Saska, "Physical Orienteering Problem for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Data Collection Planning in Environments With Obstacles," *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 3005–3012, Jul. 2019.
- [18] Meng, H., Shafik, W., Matinkhah, S.M. and Ahmad, Z., "A 5G Beam Selection Machine Learning Algorithm for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Applications," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2020, 2020.
- [19] C. Antón-Haro and X. Mestre, "Learning and Data-Driven Beam Selection for mmWave Communications: An Angle of Arrival-Based Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 20404–20415, 2019.
- [20] M. Giordani, M. Polese, A. Roy, D. Castor, and M. Zorzi, "Standalone and Non-Standalone Beam Management for 3GPP NR at mmWaves," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 123–129, Apr. 2019.

- [21] Y. Wang, Q. Li, J. Jiao, S. Wu, and Q. Zhang, "ARM: Adaptive Random-Selected Multi-Beamforming Estimation Scheme for Satellite-Based Internet of Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 63264–63276, 2019.
- [22] Y. Wang, Q. Li, J. Jiao, S. Wu, and Q. Zhang, "ARM: Adaptive Random-Selected Multi-Beamforming Estimation Scheme for Satellite-Based Internet of Things," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 63264–63276, 2019.
- [23] R. Pal, A. K. Chaitanya, and K. V. Srinivas, "Low-Complexity Beam Selection Algorithms for Millimeter-Wave Beam-space MIMO Systems," *IEEE Commun. Lett.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 768–771, Apr. 2019.
- [24] S. M. Matinkhah, W. Shafik, and M. Ghasemzadeh, "Emerging Artificial Intelligence Application: Reinforcement Learning Issues on Current Internet of Things," in *16th international Conference in information knowledge and Technology (ikt2019)*, 2019.
- [25] M. Meng et al., "BeamRaster: A Practical Fast Massive MU-MIMO System With Pre-Computed Precoders," *IEEE Trans. Mob. Comput.*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 1014–1027, May 2019.
- [26] C. Antón-Haro and X. Mestre, "Learning and Data-Driven Beam Selection for mmWave Communications: An Angle of Arrival-Based Approach," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 20404–20415, 2019.
- [27] L. Jiang and H. Jafarkhani, "Multi-User Analog Beamforming in Millimeter Wave MIMO Systems Based on Path Angle Information," *IEEE Trans. Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 608–619, Jan. 2019.
- [28] W. Shafik and S. M. Matinkhah, "How to use Erlang B to determine the blocking probability of packet loss in wireless communication," in *13th Symposium on Advances in Science & Technology*, Mashhad, 2018.
- [29] A. Asadi, S. Müller, G. H. Sim, A. Klein, and M. Hollick, "FML: Fast machine learning for 5G mmWave vehicular communications," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2018-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, 2018, pp. 1961–1969.
- [30] W. Shafik and S. M. Matinkhah, "Admitting New Requests in Fog Networks According to Erlang B Distribution," in *27th Iranian Conference on Electrical Engineering (ICEE)*, 2019, pp. 2016–2021.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Wasswa Shafik received a B.Sc. degree in Computer Engineering from Ndejje University Kampala, Uganda in 2016. He also received his MSc degree in Computer Engineering at Yazd University, Iran. He is currently a researcher at the Intelligent Connectivity Research laboratory at Yazd University. His research interests include Smart Grid, Smart Cities, Cyber Security, 5G & Beyond, and Machine Learning.

S. Mojtaba Matinkhah is an assistant professor of Computer Engineering at Yazd University, Iran. He received his B.Sc. degree in software engineering from the University of Isfahan, Iran, an M.Sc. degree in Computer Security from Tehran Polytechnic, and his Ph.D. in Computer Networks from Tehran Polytechnic. He was a scholar visitor of Mississippi State University, the USA in 2011. He is currently the head of the Intelligent Connectivity Research laboratory in Yazd. His main interests are 5G, IoT, Smart Grids, post-quantum security, Cloud-Fog-Edge computing.

Solagbade Saheed Afolabi received his B.S degree in Chemistry at the University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria in 2015. He is currently pursuing his Masters in Mineral Chemistry at Yazd University. His research area includes Coordination Chemistry, Polymer Chemistry. He is currently a researcher at the Intelligent Connectivity Research laboratory at Yazd University.

Mamman Nur Sanda received his B.S degree in Physics at the University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Nigeria in 2015. He is currently pursuing his Masters in physics at Yazd University. His research area includes Condense Matter, Solid State. He is currently a researcher at the Intelligent Connectivity Research laboratory at Yazd University.